

Developing a Cybernetic Model of Interdepartmental Logistic Interactions in SME

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Abstract : In today's competitive environment production's logistic objectives such as 'delivery reliability' and 'delivery time' and distribution's logistic objectives such as 'service level' and 'delivery delay' are attributed great importance. Especially for small and mid-sized enterprises (SME) attaining these objectives pose a key challenge. Within this context, one of the difficulties is that interactions between departments within the enterprise and their specific objectives are insufficiently taken into account and aligned. Interdepartmental independencies along with contradicting targets set within the different departments result in enterprises having sub-optimal logistic performance capability. This paper presents a research project which will systematically describe the interactions between departments and convert them into a quantifiable form.

Keywords : department-specific actuating and control variables, interdepartmental interactions, cybernetic model, logistic objectives

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